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Determinants of Women's Empowerment: An Empirical Inquiry.

Suruchi Bhatia* and Gopa Bhardwaj**

Astract

This work is an unbiased understanding of underlying characteristics of empowerment, scientifically gathered and without any feminist nuances. Social status of women has had its crests and falls all along Indian history. The main focus of the present study is on the fact that, in spite of the revolution in the number of working women, many are blocked in their attempts to gain access to higher occupational positions. The sample comprised of 30 women administrators, entrepreneurs and professionals, from various walks of life having reached a significant milestone in their life from an organizational point of view, in the Indian national scenario. These were selected on the basis of empowering behaviour exhibited by them. A qualitative method of research was implemented to have a basic understanding of the underlying factors and to establish an insight into their interplay. Along with this, a documentary analysis was undertaken to determine the domains. Based on the three categories three separate role models were proposed in the beginning, but non-compliance on tests of significance rendered only one role model to be developed. This study is just the beginning; from here the road map of success for the working women can be drawn. As empowerment is a continuous process, that needs to be designed and articulated for every individual.

Key words: Empowerment, socialization, personality & motivation, career development, successful women, role model

All over the world women are denied equal status vis- a- vis men in accessing opportunities for personal growth and social development in education, employment, marriage, family, profession and political life. Despite the quiet revolution in the number of working women, many are restricted in their attempts to gain access to higher occupational positions although no formal distinctions are made between jobs for men and jobs for women, there is a fairly clear segmentation in the labour market in most developed countries.

In many countries a few exceptional women have risen to the throne and ruled well there have also been with some women who were brilliant teachers and able administrators, but their numbers were extremely meagre. Vast majorities were busy toiling hard doing daily chores of household activities and lower types of

manual labour and menial jobs. This was perhaps due to the structure of the society where women occupied subservient position irrespective of their occupational roles. The main focus of the present study is on the fact that, in spite of the revolution in the number of working women, many are blocked in their attempts to gain access to higher occupational positions.

As we scan the research in recent past, two trends are observed.

The first indicates the lessons learnt from the women who were in powerful positions through either their own efforts or some form of inheritance / family legacy.

The second trend indicates the mechanization of ascent- where the search for meaning and empowerment focuses more on intrinsic search and ingenuity in employing resources to form a

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